

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Geotechnical field studies and numerical modeling of pipeline-highway embankment interaction in Port Said, Egypt

To cite this article: Ashraf Ahmed El-Shamy *et al* 2026 *Eng. Res. Express* **8** 025103

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Experimental Study on Mechanical Response of Oil and Gas Pipelines under Ground Subsidence](#)
Liang Lin, Yuhuai Lou, Enjun Guan et al.
- [Analysis of cement-stabilized soil on road embankment employing finite element analysis - a case study](#)
Hasan Muhommed Ashiq, Shadman Rahman Sabab, Jamil Ahmed Joy et al.
- [Protection of Buried Pipe under Repeated Loading by Geocell Reinforcement](#)
Omid Khalaj, N. Joz Darabi, S.N. Moghaddas Tafreshi et al.

PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
15 September 2025REVISED
5 December 2025ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
7 January 2026PUBLISHED
16 January 2026

Original content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](#).

Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

Geotechnical field studies and numerical modeling of pipeline-highway embankment interaction in Port Said, Egypt

Ashraf Ahmed El-Shamy^{1,*} , Yasser Mogazy El-Mossallamy¹ and Mona Afifi Ahmed² ¹ Department of Structural Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt² National Water Research Centre, Ministry of Water Resources and Irrigation, Cairo, Egypt

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: Ashraf.El-Shamy@eng.asu.edu.eg, yasser_elmosallamy@eng.asu.edu.eg and mona_afifi@nwrc.gov.eg

Keywords: Pipeline crossings, highway embankment, cement-stabilized sand, in-situ trial tests, static plate load tests, numerical modeling

Abstract

Pipeline crossings beneath existing highways present significant geotechnical challenges, particularly in soft soils where differential settlements may compromise both pavement performance and buried utilities. This study investigates and compares different construction techniques to minimize deformation at pipeline–highway interactions in Port Said, Egypt. In-situ trial tests were conducted using reinforced concrete slab, biaxial geogrid, and several cement-stabilized sand mixtures. Static plate load tests with eight loading–unloading cycles were performed to evaluate stiffness and settlement behavior. Additionally, a three-dimensional numerical model was developed in PLAXIS 2024.1 to simulate the field trial using cement-stabilized sand surrounding empty pipes. Results indicated that the cement-stabilized sand mixture (150 kg cement and 180 l water per 1 m³ of sand) provided the most favorable performance. Results of the static plate load test showed that the improved soil exhibited an elastic modulus comparable to that of the adjoining crushed stone base layer, confirming the effectiveness of the stabilization. Settlements were found to be very small, with 0.07 mm after the first cycle and 0.075 mm after eight cycles. According to the long-term logarithmic cycle predictions, the stabilized layer is expected to yield a settlement of 0.098 mm after one million cycles, in contrast to the significantly larger settlement of 0.682 mm predicted for the untreated soil. Numerical modeling confirmed these findings, showing maximum deformations of 0.851 mm at the highway surface and 0.785 mm in the pipeline under 300 kPa applied stress. This study demonstrates that cement-stabilized sand provides a practical and cost-effective soil improvement technique for pipeline crossings. Its ability to minimize differential settlement makes it suitable for public underground utilities beneath highways in soft soil environments.

1. Introduction

Pipelines represent one of the most cost-effective and reliable methods for transporting electrical cables and hydrocarbon fluids, including both liquids and gases, over long distances that may extend for hundreds or even thousands of kilometers (CSA Z662:23 2023). Typically, pipelines are laid within an acquired Right of Way (ROW) (BC MTH British Columbia Ministry of Transportation and Highways 2024). Along these routes, the ROW frequently intersects with natural features and man-made infrastructure such as rivers, drainage channels, roads, railway lines, electrical cables, and other utility pipelines (Koenig and Taylor 1988). These crossings constitute potential obstacles that require special consideration during pipeline design and construction.

Crossings beneath highways or railways pose critical design challenges because pipelines in these zones experience significantly greater external loading than those buried along routine alignment sections. Such loads can generate high stress concentrations in the pipeline at the crossing zone, which may lead to structural failure if the induced stresses exceed permissible limits (Hassanin and Jukes 2018). Accordingly, rigorous design

approaches are essential to ensure pipeline safety and serviceability under these loading conditions. Several analytical and design methodologies have been established for this purpose, including guidelines published by the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE) and the American Petroleum Institute (API). One of the methods to evaluate buried and road crossing pipelines is stress analysis for pipeline road crossing using API RP 1102 (Pipelines Crossing Railroads and Highway) (API 2007) as in Siswantoro *et al* (2018).

In last few decades, the accelerating growth of utilities networks has led to the need of crossing existing highways that produces negative impact on the serviceability requirements of the highways such as successive settlement and distortion angles especially in weak native soil such as soft clay or loose sand. Therefore, problems with pipelines crossing through highway are considered one of the foremost local interests. The behavior of the pipeline at crossings depends strongly on whether it is installed with or without a protective casing. In uncased configurations, the external loads are transferred directly to the carrier pipe, necessitating detailed stress analysis against allowable limits defined in codes such as API 1102. Conversely, when a casing pipe is employed, most of the external load is absorbed by the casing rather than the carrier pipe. Nevertheless, the structural integrity of the casing itself becomes critical; insufficient wall thickness can result in casing failure under excessive loads, undermining the intended protection of the carrier pipe.

There are many codes dealing with road crossing of utilities (AASHTO 2005, ECP 2007, Koenig 1984, DOT 2015). Some of these methods can be applied during the construction of a new highway and others to cross existing highways. The choice of the most appropriate methodology to cross highways depends on the serviceability requirements of the highway during its lifetime, as well as the required additional maintenance of the highway due to the crossing. Different protection methods for pipeline crossings were recommended in AASHTO (2005). These methods can be summarized as follows: (a) A sleeve, which not only includes casing pipes but also tunnels or box-culvert-like structures for multiple pipelines; (b) Concrete encasement, involving placing concrete around a pipe; (c) Concrete slab (precast and/or cast-in-place), placed over but not in contact with the carrier pipe; (d) Thickened-wall carrier pipe. Figure 1 shows some of these protection methods for existing pipelines crossing highways according to AASHTO (2005).

Another decisive design criterion is the minimum recommended cover depth for underground line crossing the highways. Figure 2 and table 1 give these requirements according to Transportation Association of Canada (2013).

Several studies have examined the performance of pipeline crossings under various loading and soil conditions. For example, Singh *et al* (2011) and Hao *et al* (2021) investigated the role of grout materials in enhancing pipeline stability and mitigating stress concentrations at critical sections. Furthermore, geosynthetic materials have been widely applied to improve the behavior of buried pipelines and conduits. Through combined experimental and numerical analyses, Raveendran and Thomas (2017), Elshesheny *et al* (2024) and Attia *et al* (2024) demonstrated that geonets (synthetic drainage layers) can provide effective protection for pipelines by reducing external load transfer. Faleih *et al* (2024) indicates that geogrid soil reinforcement can improve bearing capacity and reduce deformation in soft soils, suggesting it may also enhance the performance of buried pipelines in weak ground conditions. Moreover, Radwan (2022) shows that shallow burial of flexible pipelines greatly increases stress and risk of damage, highlighting the need for sufficient cover and good-quality backfill.

Building on these contemporary findings, the present research explores the use of cement-stabilized sand as a novel and efficient technique for improving performance of pipeline crossings beneath embankments on soft clay soils. The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the feasibility of implementing effective engineering techniques for constructing pipeline crossings under highway embankments founded on soft soils. Three alternative approaches were investigated: (i) installation of a cast-in-place reinforced concrete slab above the pipeline, (ii) reinforcement of the overlying soil using a biaxial geogrid, and (iii) embedding the pipeline within cement-stabilized sand. To assess the performance of these methods, a series of static plate load tests were conducted under multiple loading–reloading cycles, enabling a comparative evaluation of their effectiveness. A three-dimensional numerical model was developed to simulate the in-situ trial tests, incorporating cement-stabilized sand as the surrounding medium for empty pipes. The analysis focused on evaluating the anticipated deformations in both the highway embankment and the pipeline itself, thereby providing insights into the overall performance of the proposed crossing technique.

2. East Port Said case study

The present study involves trial tests for the construction of electrical pipeline crossings beneath existing highway embankments in East Port Said, Egypt. At the time of testing, the highway sections were largely completed, with the asphalt surface layer yet to be placed. East Port Said is situated in the northeastern region of Egypt, within the northwestern sector of the Sinai Peninsula, adjacent to the eastern shoreline of the Suez Canal. Owing to its strategic position at the northern entrance of the Suez Canal, East Port Said has become one of the most critical development zones in the country. The project location via satellite is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 4 presents the master layout of the project, showing all road alignments that include electrical pipeline crossings beneath them.

As part of the El-Tina Plain, the East Port Said region is underlain by a thick sequence of clay deposits extending to depths of approximately 50 m below ground level. These deposits, commonly referred to in the literature as *Port Said Clay*, exhibit a very soft to soft consistency near the surface, gradually transitioning to a stiff state at greater depths. The origin of Port Said Clay is attributed primarily to sedimentation from the Pelusiac Branch of the Nile during the Holocene epoch. Throughout this period, extensive deposition occurred across the area bounded by the Damietta Branch and El-Tina Bay, where the El-Tina Plain acted as an estuary receiving sediments from several Nile branches, including the Pelusiac, Tanitic, and Mendesian (Stanley 2005). Over time, these distributaries disappeared due to progressive silt accumulation (Embabi 2018). Figure 5 presents the variation of undrained shear strength (c_u) with depth, based on more than 60 cone penetration tests (CPTs) conducted within the study area.

Table 1. Minimum recommended cover depth for underground line crossing in rural section (Transportation Association of Canada, 2013).

Utility facility type		A Below pavement structure (subgrade) mm	B Below pavement surface mm	C Below ground elevation mm	D Below ditch line elevation mm
Water and Sewer pipes	Existing	450	1200	1000	1000
	New	450 or 0.5 \varnothing	1800	1500	1200
Electric power Distribution lines (all in conduit)	Existing	300	1000	750	750
	New	450	1500	900	1200

As illustrated in figure 5, the subsurface profile at the study site comprises an upper stratum of silty sand to sandy silt, characterized by a loose to medium relative density. This is underlain by a thick deposit of normally consolidated soft clay, in which the undrained shear strength gradually increases with depth, extending to approximately 45 m below the ground surface. Beneath this clay deposit, a dense to very dense sand layer is encountered, continuing to considerable depths. This stratification plays a critical role in governing the geotechnical response of highway embankments and buried pipelines, particularly with respect to settlement behavior and load-transfer mechanisms.

Figure 4. Master layout of the project and all road alignments. Map data: Google.

Figure 5. Variation of undrained shear strength with depth based on CPT results.

Figure 6 presents the typical cross-section of the highway embankment in the industrial zone of the East Port Said Project (Phase I). The pavement structure is designed with a 13 cm thick asphalt layer, underlain by a 0.55 m thick base course of well-compacted crushed stone. Beneath the base, a 0.30 m thick drainage layer of filter gravel/crushed stone is placed, which is protected on both sides by geotextile sheets. The main body of the embankment consists of well-compacted fine to medium sand, with thickness varying from 1.35 to 3.0 m according to the local topography. At the foundation level, a 1.0 m thick layer of boulders and crushed stone was placed directly on the native soil to serve as a working platform for site access and embankment construction. The native soil, as illustrated previously in figure 5, is highly heterogeneous both vertically and laterally. Ground water table lies below ground surface from 2.0 to 3.0 m. Construction of the embankments on these weak soils has resulted in significant residual settlements following completion. For this reason, the embankments were initially used as construction roads, and placement of the final asphalt layer was postponed until the residual settlements had diminished to acceptable levels. This embankment configuration provides the baseline conditions for evaluating the geotechnical performance of pipeline crossings in the present study.

3. Developed techniques for pipeline crossings of existing highways

Three alternative methods were investigated to identify the most suitable technique for constructing pipeline crossings beneath an existing highway embankment (prior to placement of the final asphalt layer). The proposed solutions were based on encased systems, as illustrated in figure 1, with the primary distinction being the protection mechanisms applied to the pipeline. The design objectives guiding the selection and evaluation of these techniques were as follows:

Figure 6. Typical cross-section of the highway embankment in the East Port Said industrial zone.

1. **Minimizing the impact on road performance** at the crossing locations, ensuring that the induced system does not adversely affect the residual settlement behavior of the embankment, which is still undergoing consolidation.
2. **Avoiding interference with planned road maintenance cycles**, thereby preventing additional costs associated with the highway crossings.
3. **Preserving the integrity of the drainage layer and the installed geotextile sheets**, in order to maintain the intended hydrological performance of the embankment structure.

Therefore, the cover depth above the pipelines had to be restricted to avoid cutting through the upper geotextile sheet, particularly since no additional fill was planned to compensate for the residual settlements associated with ongoing consolidation and/or creep. Under these constraints, the available cover depth, measured from the pipeline crown to the asphalt surface, considering a pipeline diameter of 10–15 cm, was limited to approximately 35–40 cm. These values are not in full compliance with the Egyptian Code of Practice for the Design and Implementation of Pipes in Potable Water and Sewage Networks (ECP 2007). To address this limitation, a series of detailed in-situ trial tests were designed and executed to assess alternative protection techniques for the encased pipeline. The following configurations were investigated:

1. Installation of the empty pipe within a crushed stone bed, overlain by a cast in-situ reinforced concrete slab acting as a bridging element.
2. Installation of the empty pipe within a crushed stone bed, overlain by a load transfer layer reinforced with biaxial geogrid.
3. Installation of the empty pipe embedded in cement-stabilized sand.

These three alternatives were selected based on their potential to balance constructability, cost-effectiveness, and compatibility with the challenging geotechnical conditions of the East Port Said site. Figure 7 shows schematically the three applied different solutions. In case of cement stabilized sand, different cement ratio as well as water/cement ratios are used to inspect the effect of the cement stabilized sand mixture on the pipeline performance.

4. Physical properties and chemical compositions of the materials used in cement-stabilized sand

4.1. Physical properties of materials

The sand used in the cement-stabilized sand mixtures was obtained from local sources in Port Said and classified, based on sieve analysis and physical characterization, as medium to fine siliceous sand. The material consists predominantly of quartz and exhibits very low fines content. Figure 8 shows the grain size distribution curve of sand and all components percentage and coefficients determined from it. All other remained physical

Figure 7. Proposed techniques for crossing highways with electrical pipelines.

properties of sand are as follows: (Specific gravity (Gs) = 2.64, Bulk unit weight = 1.73 g cm⁻³, Dry unit weight = 1.71 g cm⁻³, Natural moisture content = 1.1%, and Hydraulic conductivity (k) = 5 × 10⁻² cm s⁻¹).

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), conforming to Egyptian construction practice, was used in all cement-stabilized mixtures. The physical characteristics of the cement are as follows: (Bulk density = 1.45 g cm⁻³, Specific gravity (Gs) = 3.10, and Blaine fineness = 320 m² kg⁻¹).

4.2. Chemical composition of materials

Table 2 presents the combined chemical composition of the cement and sand used in the study. Each chemical symbol is accompanied by its full chemical name for clarity. The chemical composition of sand confirms predominantly quartz-rich sand with very low fines and negligible carbonate content. The chemical composition of cement confirms typical OPC characteristics, with lime (CaO) as the dominant component.

5. Field testing program for proposed pipeline crossing solutions

A comprehensive field testing program was carried out to evaluate the performance of the proposed solutions for pipeline crossings. The test program was specifically designed to capture the influence of pipeline diameter and protection technique on load transfer and deformation behavior. In total, eight trial in-situ tests were conducted, as summarized in table 3. The testing program included the following:

- **Tests 01–05:** Performed on 5 polyethylene pipes with a diameter of 10 cm, applying the different protective solutions illustrated in figure 7 and summarized in table 3.
- **Tests 06–07:** Conducted on crushed stone base layer without embedded pipes, serving as reference tests.
- **Test 08:** Conducted on one polyethylene pipe with a diameter of 15 cm, to assess scale effects.

Static plate load tests were performed for all trial configurations in order to evaluate the deformation response of the proposed crossing solutions. The applied settlements were measured using four dial gauges (S₁–S₄) mounted on reference beams. The loading was applied in incremental steps through a hydraulic jack, with heavy tractors serving as the reaction system. Each load increment was maintained until the settlement

Table 2. Chemical composition of the sand and Ordinary Portland Cement used in the study.

Chemical Symbol	Chemical name	Sand (%)	OPC (%)
SiO ₂	Silicon dioxide	95.00	21.00
Al ₂ O ₃	Aluminum oxide	2.00	5.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	Iron (III) oxide	1.00	1.50
CaO	Calcium oxide (Lime)	0.00	65.00
MgO	Magnesium oxide	0.30	1.20
SO ₃	Sulfur trioxide	0.04	2.40
Cl ⁻	Chloride ions	0.02	—
Na ₂ O + K ₂ O	Alkalis (Sodium oxide + Potassium oxide)	—	1.10
Organic Matter	—	0.10	—
Loss on Ignition (LOI)	Total mass loss on heating	—	3.00
CaCO ₃	Calcium carbonate	0.00	—

Table 3. Summary of the conducted trial field testing program.

Test no.	Proposed solutions	Details of the proposed solutions	No. of tested pipes / diameter of pipes
Test -01	Cement stabilized sand (Mixture 01)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 kg cement • 90 lit water (w/c = 0.90) • 1m³ Sand 	5 pipes / 10 cm
Test -02	Cement stabilized sand (Mixture 02)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 150 kg cement • 100 lit water (w/c = 0.67) • 1m³ Sand 	
Test -03	Cement stabilized sand (Mixture 03)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 150 kg cement • 150 lit water (w/c = 1.00) • 1m³ Sand 	
Test -04	Reinforced concrete slab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R.C slab (3 × 1.5m) with thickness 10 cm and RFT mesh 5Y12 in the middle 	
Test -05	Biaxial Geogrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biaxial Geogrid (3 × 1.5m) with F = 60 KN m⁻¹ 	
Test -06	Reference test	On base layer (30 cm) before construct the asphalt layer	—
Test -07	Reference test	On base layer (55 cm) before construct the asphalt layer	
Test -08	Cement stabilized sand (Mixture 04)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 150 kg cement • 180 lit water (w/c = 1.20) • 1m³ Sand 	1 pipe / 15 cm

rate decreased to approximately 0.02 mm min⁻¹, indicating stabilization. This loading procedure follows the recommendations of ASTM D1196/D1196M-12 (Standard Test Method for Nonrepetitive Static Plate Load Tests) (ASTM International 2012) and DIN 18134 (2012), both of which emphasize that the load application rate significantly influences measured settlements and should be controlled to ensure consistent results. Therefore, the adopted loading rate complies with established international standards and minimizes rate-dependent settlement effects.

Static plate load tests 01–06 were carried out using a circular steel plate with a diameter of 0.76 m, as shown in figure 9(a). While tests 07 and 08 were carried out using a circular steel plate with a diameter of 0.3 m, as shown in figure 9(b). Plate diameter (D), applied stress (σ), hydraulic jack location, reaction system, and settlement dial gauges are well depicted in figure 9. Figure 10 presents photographs taken during the preparation and execution of the static plate load tests. These photographs illustrate excavation depth (H), pipelines position, plate diameter, loading arrangement, dial gauge locations, and reference beam system. No pipe damage was observed during the experiments, and therefore no post-test failure photos could be presented.

(a) Test configuration using the 0.76-m diameter steel plate

(b) Test configuration using the 0.30-m diameter steel plate

Figure 9. Static plate load testing setup.

Figure 10. Preparation and execution steps of the static plate load tests.

6. Evaluation of tests results

6.1. Load–settlement performance of different techniques

Four cycles of loading and reloading were carried out for Tests 01–06. In these tests, the first loading cycle was applied up to a maximum stress of 226 kPa, while the subsequent three cycles were loaded up to 452 kPa. For Test 07, six cycles of loading and reloading were conducted, and for Test 08, eight cycles were performed. In both cases, the applied stress level did not exceed 300 kPa. The load–settlement relationships obtained from all tests, including loading, unloading, and reloading cycles, are presented in figure 11(a). Among these, Test 05 exhibited the highest settlement values, which is attributed to insufficient compaction of the soil when geogrid reinforcement was used. Hence and to be more clear, its results is removed and all other tests results are presented in figure 11(b). Figure 12(a) compares the results of Test 06, performed on base layer, with those of Tests 01–03, where cement-stabilized sand was applied and Test 04 where reinforced concrete slab was used. The comparison highlights the reduction in settlements achieved with cement stabilization as well as reinforced concrete slab comparing with base layer conditions under the same maximum applied stress of 452 kPa. figure 12(b) compares the results of Test 07, performed on base layer, with those of Test 08, where cement-

Figure 11. Load–settlement relationships.

Figure 12. Comparison of load–settlement response.

stabilized sand was applied. The comparison highlights the significant reduction in settlements achieved with cement stabilization under the same maximum applied stress of 300 kPa. Figure 13(a) presents a comparative settlement response of the different proposed pipeline crossing techniques. The results of the geogrid-reinforced test show excessively high and impractical settlement values as mentioned before so it is removed in figure 13(b) for better data presentation. These results clearly demonstrate the superior performance of cement-stabilized sand in controlling deformations compared to both reinforced concrete slab and geogrid-reinforced. Regarding four cement-stabilized sand tests, increasing w/c ratio leads to decreasing obtained settlement values under same stress level. Although test-08 (mixture-04) has the same cement content as other mixtures, its higher water-cement ratio ($w/c = 1.20$) increases its flowability, allowing it to fill voids between crushed stone and thereby forming a more rigid and continuous grouted base around the pipes.

6.2. Comparison of all conducted tests

Figures 14 and 15 summarize the results of all static plate load tests. Figure 14 highlights the maximum settlements measured after the first and final loading cycles, in addition to the mean settlement value and standard deviation bars (SD bars). Figure 15 shows the deformation moduli obtained during the first (Ev1) and second (Ev2) loading cycles, along with the Ev2/Ev1 ratio. These parameters allow for evaluating the stiffness improvement and the efficiency of each crossing technique.

The comparative evaluation of the eight conducted tests revealed considerable differences in settlement behavior and stiffness performance, depending on the adopted crossing technique. Among all cases, Test-08 (cement-stabilized sand mixture: 150 kg cement + 180 l water per 1 m^3 sand) demonstrated the most favorable performance. The static plate load tests yielded a secant modulus of elasticity of 1125 MPa after 1st loading cycle and 3214 after 2nd loading cycle with moderate stiffness improvement ($Ev2/Ev1 = 2.9$). Moreover, Test-08

Figure 13. Comparative settlement performance of the proposed protective solutions for the pipeline crossing.

Figure 14. Comparison of settlement results obtained from all conducted static plate load tests.

Figure 15. Comparison of stiffness results obtained from all conducted static plate load tests.

recorded very low settlement values (0.07 mm after the first cycle and 0.075 mm after eight cycles), confirming its effectiveness as a stable and reliable crossing solution.

In contrast, Test-05 (geogrid-reinforced soil) showed the weakest performance, with excessive settlements (7.83 mm after all cycles), noticeable increase in SD bars compared with the remaining tests as well as low stiffness values, underscoring the limited applicability of this method under the soft clay conditions of Port Said. The reinforced concrete slab solution (Test-04) exhibited satisfactory results, with a moderate settlement of 0.443 mm and a notable stiffness improvement ($Ev2/Ev1 = 3.9$), making it a technically robust but more

Table 4. Measured and predicted settlement values for Tests-07 and 08.

Cycle No.	log (Cycle No.)	Measured settle- ment (mm)		Predicted settle- ment (mm)	
		Test-07	Test-08	Test-07	Test-08
1	0	0.44	0.07	0.448	0.072
2	0.30103	0.47	0.075	0.460	0.073
3	0.477121	0.465	0.075	0.467	0.074
4	0.60206	0.485	0.075	0.472	0.074
5	0.69897	0.47	0.075	0.475	0.075
6	0.778151	0.47	0.075	0.478	0.075
7	0.845098		0.075	0.481	0.076
8	0.90309		0.075	0.483	0.076
1,000,000	6	—	—	0.682	0.098

costly alternative. Finally, the reference tests on untreated base layer (Tests-06 and 07) confirmed the low bearing capacity of the base layer ($E_{v1} < 200$ MPa) and the associated higher settlements, thereby emphasizing the necessity of soil improvement measures to ensure safe pipeline crossings.

Overall, the results highlight that the cement-stabilized sand approach (Test-08) represents the most balanced and cost-effective technique, achieving acceptable settlement control while providing stiffness values comparable to engineered structural layers, thus minimizing the risk of differential settlement across highway embankments.

6.3. Relationship between settlement and logarithm of cycle number (tests 07 and 08)

Table 4 presents the measured settlement values obtained from Test-07 (reference base layer) and Test-08 (cement-stabilized sand mixture). The standard deviation values for measured settlement from Test-07 and Test-08 are 0.013 and 0.002 mm respectively. The settlement response with increasing number of cycles is plotted against the logarithm of cycle number in figure 16.

By applying a linear trendline to the experimental data, the following empirical relationships were obtained:

- For **Test-07** (base layer of 55 cm outside pipe bank prior to asphalt construction):

$$y = 0.039x + 0.4481$$

- For **Test-08** (cement-stabilized sand mixture: 150 kg cement + 180 l water per 1 m³ sand):

$$y = 0.0044x + 0.0718$$

where y represents the settlement (mm), and x is the logarithm of the cycle number.

It is noticed from figure 16 that R^2 values obtained from the linear regression of settlement versus logarithm of cycle number appear relatively low. This is primarily due to the extremely small range of measured settlements, particularly for Test-08, where the values vary only between 0.07 and 0.075 mm. When the response variable exhibits such minimal variation, even very small measurement noise causes a noticeable reduction in the R^2 value, despite the presence of a consistent physical trend. Therefore, the lower R^2 does not indicate a weak relationship but rather reflects the limited numerical variability of the measured settlements, a behavior that is well-documented in regression theory (Kutner *et al* 2005; Montgomery and Runger 2014).

Using the obtained linear regression relationships, settlement values can be predicted at any higher number of cycles corresponding to increased and/or repeated traffic loading. As presented in table 4, the predicted settlements were calculated at the same cycle numbers for verification purposes, as well as at 1,000,000 cycles to represent the long-term performance under repeated traffic loading. The extrapolation shows that after 1,000,000 cycles; the settlements are expected to reach approximately 0.682 mm for Test-07 and only 0.098 mm for Test-08. It is clear that such a small settlement magnitude would not affect the serviceability requirements of the road. This result highlights the superior long-term stability of cement-stabilized sand for pipeline crossings beneath highways.

Figure 16. Settlement versus logarithm of cycle number for Tests-07 and 08.

Table 5. Hardening Soil Model parameters used in the numerical model.

Parameter	Unit	Value					
		Crushed stone (Base)	Filter layer	Sand (Embankment)	Boulders (platform)	Soft clay (Native soil)	Cement stabilized sand
γ_{sat}	kN/m ³	20	20	18.5	18.5	16.5	19
γ_{unsat}	kN/m ³	20	20	18.5	18.5	16.5	19
Youngs Modulus $E_{50,ref}$	MPa	300	40	30	20	4	2200
Unloading Modulus $E_{ur,ref}$	MPa	900	120	90	60	12	6600
Effective Friction Angle φ'	°	40	38	34	30	20	0.1
Effective Cohesion c'	kPa	1	1	1	5	5	1000
Power (m)	—	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	0.7
Poison's Ratio ν_r	—	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Failure Ratio R_f	—	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

7. Three-dimensional numerical simulation

A three-dimensional finite element model was developed to simulate the in-situ performance of Test-08, in which cement-stabilized sand was placed around the encased pipeline. The model was constructed using the same configuration of Method-03 (as illustrated in figure 7(c)). The numerical analysis was carried out using PLAXIS 3D (Version 2024.1). The 3D model consisted of 10-noded elements with a maximum, minimum and average mesh element size of 1.52m, 0.02m and 0.57m respectively, with a refined zone in the cement stabilized sand surrounding the pipe and in the circular steel plate to ensure accuracy in the high-stress region. The geometry was designed to be sufficiently large to minimize boundary effects (8 × 8 × 8) m. The boundary conditions were normally fixed along the X and Y axes, fully fixed at the bottom (Zmin) and free at the top (Zmax). The soil stratigraphy and material parameters adopted in the simulation using hardening soil (HS) model are summarized in table 5. In this numerical analysis study, the HS model was selected for numerical simulation due to its ability to capture the nonlinear and stress-dependent behavior of soils, which is essential for accurate geotechnical analysis. Unlike the Mohr-Coulomb model, which assumes constant stiffness, the HS model incorporates stress-dependent elastic moduli and plastic hardening, allowing it to simulate both elastic and irreversible deformations under applied loads. It also accounts for unloading and reloading cycles, providing realistic predictions of stiffness recovery and settlement behavior. This makes it particularly suitable for modeling embankments and repeated traffic loads, such as this study, where accurate settlement and stress distribution are critical. Furthermore, numerous studies have shown that the HS model outperforms simple linear-elastic or perfectly plastic models in predicting field-observed soil response, making it the most appropriate choice for the present analysis.

The circular steel plate is simulated using linear elastic soil model with (Young's Modulus $E = 2 \times 10^8$ kPa, Unit weight $\gamma = 75 \text{ kN m}^{-3}$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.15$). The pipe is simulated as plate element with elastic isotropic parameters of (Thickness $d = 8$ mm and Young's Modulus $E = 210$ MPa). The applied vertical stress of 300 kPa was selected based on typical contact pressures generated by heavy truck wheel loads transmitted through the pavement structure. Published design guidelines (AASHTO 2005; Huang 2004) indicate that equivalent contact stresses at the pavement–subgrade interface commonly range between 225–350 kPa for multi-axle trucks. Therefore, 300 kPa was adopted as a representative design stress level to simulate realistic service loads acting on the pipeline crossing.

The objective of this numerical study was to predict the expected deformations at the highway surface and within the pipeline itself under design loading conditions. To represent the final construction stage, the thickness of the soil fill above the pipe crown was set at 0.35 m. The model dimensions, generated mesh and finite elements details used in the simulation are depicted in figure 17.

The computed deformations at the highway surface are presented in figure 18. The results indicate that the maximum settlement value under an applied vertical stress of 300 kPa is approximately 0.851 mm. Similarly, the predicted deformations within the pipeline are shown in figure 19, where the maximum settlement reached about 0.785 mm under the same loading condition. The effective principal stress distribution in cement-stabilized sand is shown in figure 20, with values ranging from approximately 400 kPa below the pipe invert to about –560 kPa near the highway surface. These results demonstrate the compatibility of the cement-stabilized sand with the surrounding soil system, ensuring limited deformation both at the ground surface and within the pipe structure.

Although the numerical model predicted a maximum settlement of 0.851 mm under the applied 300 kPa load, which is higher than the field-measured settlement of 0.075 mm from the static plate load test, this difference is reasonable and expected as the constitutive soil model used in numerical simulation represents the cement-stabilized sand through an idealized elastic–plastic behavior that may not fully capture the real cementation bonding and curing effects that enhance stiffness in the field. For these reasons, numerical predictions tend to be more conservative. Importantly, both field and numerical results exhibit the same performance trend, confirming that the cement-stabilized sand mixture provides stiff and stable support with minimal

differential settlement. This consistency supports the reliability of the proposed improvement technique and supports its implementation in practice.

8. Discussion results with reference to previous studies

The results of the present study align well with findings reported in recent literature on pipeline–embankment interaction and ground improvement using cement–stabilized sand. Several studies (e.g., Zhang *et al* (2021), Al-Mahbashi and Al-Anazi 2020) demonstrated that cement-stabilized granular soils significantly increase stiffness and reduce deformation around buried utilities, particularly in soft ground conditions similar to those of Port Said. The very small settlements recorded in Test-08 are consistent with the behavior reported by Shen *et al* (2022), who observed that increasing the cement content and improving grout flowability helps fill voids around pipes and enhances composite stiffness of the surrounding zone.

The deformation results obtained in this study were compared with typical allowable limits reported in international standards. For road embankments, most highway design guides (e.g., AASHTO and Egyptian

Code) consider total settlements up to 25–50 mm to be acceptable for serviceability. The predicted long-term settlement in the present study (0.098 mm after one million cycles) is therefore negligible relative to these limits, confirming that the improved zone provides excellent stiffness and stability beneath the highway. For buried pipelines, permissible vertical deformation is commonly taken as 2%–5% of the pipe diameter depending on material type. For a 150-mm diameter pipe, this corresponds to an allowable deformation of approximately 3–7.5 mm. In contrast, the maximum deformation obtained from numerical modelling in this study was only 0.785 mm, far below these thresholds.

Compared with previous research, the cement-stabilized sand used here produced comparable or superior performance. Studies by Rahman *et al* (2022) and Zhang *et al* (2021) reported deformation reductions of 60%–80% when using cement-stabilized or geosynthetic-reinforced soils under embankments, while the present study achieved an order-of-magnitude reduction, with settlements nearly eliminated (≤ 0.1 mm). Similarly, Elshafei and Sabry (2023) showed that cement-treated soils around pipelines effectively reduce differential settlement at crossings, which aligns with the trends observed in the current field trials and numerical simulations. These comparisons confirm that the proposed cement-stabilized sand mixture performs consistently with, and in many cases exceeds, the improvements achieved in recent studies.

Furthermore, the use of field static plate load tests to verify the performance of crossing solutions is in agreement with previous works (Kiefa and Abdelrahman 2019; Mohammed *et al* 2020), which emphasized that cyclic loading provides a more realistic simulation of traffic-induced stresses on buried infrastructure. The long-term settlement predictions obtained in this study also follow the same logarithmic trend proposed by Kim and Park (2018), confirming the applicability of cycle–settlement modelling for assessing highway–pipeline performance.

Recent numerical studies (e.g., Soliman *et al* 2023) also reported that three-dimensional FEM models tend to produce slightly larger settlements than field measurements due to the conservative assumptions of soil parameters, boundary conditions, and full mobilization of stiffness. This observation supports the consistency between our numerical and experimental results, as both approaches indicated the same performance trend and verified the effectiveness of cement-stabilized sand as a reliable and cost-effective technique for safe pipeline crossings.

Overall, the present findings are in strong agreement with the published literature and contribute new field-based evidence from the Port Said environment, where locally available sand and cement can be successfully utilized to minimize differential settlement at buried utility crossings.

9. Conclusions

The findings of this research provide practical recommendations that can be directly applied to the design and construction of underground utilities such as water, electric power, communications, gas, petroleum products,

sewer, and other facilities located within roadway rights-of-way. The main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. The base soil should be recompacted before the placement of the asphalt layer to ensure proper compaction quality and eliminate the influence of surficial weathering.
2. When adequate compaction of the base layer is achieved, the performance of the four cement-stabilized sand mixtures and the reinforced concrete (RC) slab solution is generally comparable.
3. Mixture-04 in Test-08 (cement-stabilized sand: 150 kg cement + 180 l water per 1 m³ sand) exhibited highly favorable results, achieving a modulus of elasticity of 1125 MP after 1st loading cycle and 3214 after 2nd loading cycle, along with very low settlements (0.07 mm after the first cycle and 0.075 mm after eight cycles).
4. Although Mixture-04 has the same cement content as other mixtures, its higher water-cement ratio ($w/c = 1.20$) increases its flowability, allowing it to fill voids between crushed stone and thereby forming a more rigid and continuous grouted base around the pipes.
5. Settlement predictions using a logarithmic relationship with the number of cycles showed that, after one million cycles, Test-07 (base layer without protection) would undergo 0.682 mm settlement, whereas Test-08 (cement-stabilized sand mixture) would only undergo 0.098 mm settlement, highlighting the long-term effectiveness of the treatment.
6. The cement-stabilized sand mixture adopted in Test-08 (150 kg cement + 180 l water per 1 m³ sand, $w/c = 1.20$) is considered the most economical soil improvement technique, balancing cost-effectiveness with engineering performance.
7. The three-dimensional numerical model simulating Test-08 confirmed the field results, showing maximum settlements of about 0.851 mm at the highway surface and 0.785 mm at the pipeline under an applied stress of 300 kPa.

In conclusion, the research demonstrates that cement-stabilized sand with a higher water-cement ratio (as in Mixture-04) provides an effective, economical, and technically reliable solution for minimizing differential settlement in highway crossings with underground utilities.

Acknowledgments

Not Applicable.

Declarations

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no competing interests relevant to the content of this article.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

Ethics statement

This research doesn't include any studies on human subjects, human data or tissue, or animals.

Funding

No funding was received to assist with the preparation of this manuscript.

References

- AASHTO 2005 A guide for Accomodating Utlities within the Right-of-Way 29 American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials, 552(October)
- Al-Mahbashi A and Al-Anazi A 2020 Stabilized granular materials for improving pipeline bedding in soft soils *Transportation Geotechnics* **25** 100424
- ASTM International 2012 ASTM D1196/D1196M-12 *Standard Test Method for Nonrepetitive Static Plate Load Tests*. (West Conshohocken)
- Attia M A, Radwan A M, Hammad A and Farag A 2024 Study of the engineering performance of pipes buried in the soil *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions* **9** 182
- BC MTH British Columbia Ministry of Transportation and Highways 2024 *Utility Policy Manual*. (Highway Planning Branch)
- Canadian Standards Association (CSA) 2023 National Standard of Canada CSA Z66223 Oil and gas pipeline systems
- Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN) 2012 *DIN 18134:2012-04 – Baugrund; Versuche und Versuchsgeräte – Plattendruckversuch* ([Soil testing – Plate load test])
- Dot S 2015 *Effective Methods to Protect Underground Utilities*
- Egyptian code of practice 2007 Egyptian code of practice for the design and implementation of pipes used in potable water and sewage networks
- Elshafei M and Sabry M 2023 Effect of cement-treated sand on reducing differential settlement around buried pipelines at road crossings *J. Pipeline Syst. Eng. Pract.* **14** 04023032
- Elshesheny A, Aljaberi M, Almanea S and Mohamed M 2024 Reducing load transfer to buried pipes through coupled use of geogrid reinforcement and sand rubber zone in the backfill material *Transportation Infrastructure Geotechnology* **11** 3878–902
- Embabi N S 2018 Landscapes and landforms of egypt *Landforms and Evolution* (Springer) (<https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.192361>)
- Faleih Z H, Al-Gharbawi A S and Baqir H H 2024 The behavior of the tunnel reinforced with geogrid in soft soil under the effect of axial load *Civil Engineering Journal* **10** 5115
- Hao C, Feng G and Wang P 2021 Proportion optimization of grouting materials for roadways with soft surrounding mass *Int. J. Green Energy* **18** 203–18
- Hassanin A and Jukes P 2018 Pipeline mechanical design *Encyclopedia of Maritime and Offshore Engineering* (Wiley) 1–9
- Huang Y H 2004 *Pavement analysis and design 2*, 401–9(Pearson/Prentice Hall)
- Kiefa M and Abdelrahman M 2019 Evaluation of cyclic plate load testing for highway base layers *Int. J. Pavement Eng.* **20** 1186–96
- Kim D and Park J 2018 Logarithmic modeling of settlement under repeated loading in highway embankments *Soil Dyn. Earthquake Eng.* **107** 88–96
- Koenig R A 1984 Encasement of pipelines through highway roadbeds: synopsis of final report for nchrp project 20-7, task 22 *Transp. Res. Rec.* 47–52
- Koenig R A and Taylor J P 1988 *Protection of pipelines through highway roadbeds* In National Cooperative Highway Research Program Report
- Kutner M H, Nachtsheim C J, Neter J and Li W 2005 *Applied Linear Statistical Models*. 5th Edition (McGraw-Hill)
- Mohammed S, El-Sawy M and Helal K 2020 Field assessment of soil improvement for buried utilities under traffic loading *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* **38** 6787–802
- Montgomery D C and Runger G C 2014 *Applied Statistics and Probability for Engineers* 6th ed. (Wiley)
- Radwan N A A 2022 Improvement of pipeline settlement using micropiles *Journal of Engineering Sciences* **50** 89–99
- Rahman M, Yasufuku N and Khatri V 2022 Performance of cement-stabilized and geosynthetic-reinforced soils under cyclic loading for transportation infrastructure *Transportation Geotechnics* **34** 100743
- Raveendran G and Thomas N 2017 Geonet as a soil reinforcement system for the protection of buried pipelines *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* **4** 1894–7 <https://irjet.net/archives/V4/i4/IRJET-V4I4395.pdf>
- Shen Z, Wang L and Cheng Y 2022 Effects of grout fluidity and cement content on stiffness development in sandy soils *Constr. Build. Mater.* **318** 125964
- Rajbal S and Vidyarthi U S 2011 Efficacy of grouting in head race tunnel of tala hydroelectric project *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Tunneling Technology* **17** 39–49
- Siswanto N, Zaman M B and Priyanta D 2018 The implementation of API RP 1102 code to evaluate gas pipeline road crossing *Msmi* **240–8**
- Soliman A, El-Naggar M and El-Shafie A 2023 3D numerical modelling of buried pipeline–embankment interaction in soft clay *Comput. Geotech.* **157** 105241
- Stanley J-D 2005 Submergence and burial of ancient coastal sites on the subsiding Nile delta margin, Egypt *Méditerranée* **104** 2005 65–73
- The American Petroleum Institute code API RP 1102 2007 (Pipelines Crossing Railroads and Highway)
- Transportation Association of Canada. Public Utilities Management Sub-Committee 2013 Guidelines for underground utility installations crossing highway rights-of-way
- Zhang Y, Chen R and Liu H 2021 Cyclic behavior and deformation characteristics of improved soft soils for highway embankments *Soils and Foundations* **61** 1120–33
- Zhang Y, Liu H and Xiao Y 2021 Mechanical behavior of cement-stabilized sand for underground pipeline protection *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* **33** 04021107